

NAIRR Portal Report

Supplement

September 2, 2024 - January 31, 2026

Survey: October 2, 2024 - January 2, 2025

Focus Groups: October 7, 2024 - January 27, 2025

Workshop: February 4-5, 2025

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1 Executive Summary

The National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource (NAIRR) Pilot serves as a proof-of-concept for a national research infrastructure that supports innovative, AI-enabled research and education. The pilot is funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) in partnership with twelve other federal agencies and twenty-six non-governmental partners. According to the NAIRR Task Force Report published in 2023, the NAIRR Pilot portal is a key component of the NAIRR, integrating computing, data, and training resources to support open AI research and research that uses AI.

The NSF-funded SGX3 Center of Excellence for Science Gateways has led the effort to provide an initial NAIRR Pilot portal and a robust plan for the future NAIRR portal. The NSF NAIRR Supplement project entitled “Community Discovery for Near-Term NAIRR Pilot Portal Functionality” is an effort to enhance the NAIRR Pilot Portal and to engage a wide variety of stakeholders to provide feedback and to guide the next phases of the portal as it grows from being NSF-focused to community-driven and sets the stage for the NAIRR Portal.

This report is about the component to engage the community. We approached the topic with three efforts to collect community feedback: an online survey that received 1,234 answers, 6 online focus groups of two hours each, 2 in-person focus groups at the Gateways conference, and a two-day, in-person workshop. These different formats assured that we could reach a wide audience and allowed information gathering and ideation around the NAIRR Pilot Portal and visions for the NAIRR Portal.

Participants in the survey, focus groups, and workshop emphasized the need for **accessible, role-based learning support**, including **multilingual tutorials, AI-driven help, live office hours, and mentorship**. To

ease access to **AI-capable infrastructure**, users recommended replacing technical jargon with **goal-based categories**, integrating familiar tools like Jupyter and GitHub, and **standardizing resource allocation**. **Responsible AI** and **FAIR principles** were widely supported, with calls for **secure data environments**, and **reproducibility tracking**, potentially via “portals-within-the-portal.” The NAIRR Portal should serve a broad range of users from students to senior researchers through **personalized, multilingual interfaces, guided workflows, smart filtering, and customizable dashboards**. Key design priorities include **transparency and community engagement**, supported by federated governance and collaboration features such as chat, project dashboards, and explainable AI recommendations. **Structured training paths and certification programs** will further promote workforce development and smooth access.

Through user-centered design, secure AI support, and strong community involvement, the NAIRR Portal is poised to become a cornerstone of the national AI infrastructure. These findings will directly inform the next design and development phases.

*NAIRR Portal Workshop Group Photo
was taken on February 5, 2025, Day 2 of the workshop*

2 Goals of the Supplement

The NAIRR Pilot Portal supplement goals are as follows:

1. Determine short-term capabilities for the portal that can serve the community over the next three years, as well as a longer-term view of how the portal can serve the NAIRR community during the next five-to-ten years.
2. Provide a community-informed recommendation for phased implementation of portal capabilities in the NAIRR Pilot portal and provide an initial design of the NAIRR Pilot Portal.
3. Develop and provide functionalities to enable better engagement with users of NAIRR Pilot resources, including implementation of support and communications features to engage the community.
4. Develop and deploy new visualizations that showcase NAIRR Pilot investments and activities.

5. Actively meet community needs by continuously fulfilling user requirements and enhancements to the NAIRR Pilot portal that provide up-to-date information and user engagement. An example of this is the integration of NAIRR demonstration projects.

The supplement was executed in multiple phases as detailed below: Survey Planning, Focus Group Planning, and a NAIRR Portal Workshop.

3 Survey Planning

Beginning in Fall 2024, SGX3 partnered with The University of Texas at Austin (UT Austin) Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) Evaluation Services team to collaborate on the data collection, analysis, and reporting for the NAIRR supplement project. The SGX3 and TACC evaluation teams have been employing a mixed-methods approach to assess community needs and gather formative data to inform the design of both short- and long-term portals. The guiding questions are as follows:

- **User needs and expectations:** What are the needs and expectations of potential NAIRR portal users, including researchers, educators, students, and industry professionals?
- **Portal features and functionality:** What features and functionalities should be included in the NAIRR portal, such as data management tools, collaboration platforms, and educational resources?
- **AI-related research activities:** What AI-related research activities are stakeholders currently engaged in doing, and how can the NAIRR portal support these activities as well as activities that are envisioned for the future?
- **Education and training:** What educational resources and training programs should be offered through the NAIRR portal that would most benefit the community and stakeholders?
- **Governance:** What are stakeholders' perspectives on governance in AI research, and how can the NAIRR portal promote responsible AI development and use?

The initial step of the process was to have the SGX3 team and TACC evaluators thoroughly review the NAIRR Task Force Report to develop the NAIRR Portal Development Survey. The survey uses both closed- and open-ended items to understand NAIRR Pilot portal users' and potential NAIRR portal users' AI-related research activities; needs for portal features, functionalities, and resources; feedback on the interface design; and expectations of governance in AI research. Prior to the full administration of the survey, it was pilot tested with a small group of select stakeholders and revised based on their feedback.

The final survey was administered online to a wide variety of stakeholders via Qualtrics from October 2, 2024 through January 2, 2025. Anonymous survey links were distributed through SGX3 Slack Workspace channels and community partners, including the Statewide California Earthquake Center (SCEC) community and Massachusetts Green HPC (MGHPCC). Direct emails to request survey participation were sent to the following stakeholder groups:

- Subscribers to the SGX3 mailing list
- Members of the NAIRR Pilot portal user list, including:
 - Authors of the NAIRR Task Force Report
 - Recipients of NAIRR Pilot resource allocations
 - Representatives of NAIRR Pilot resource providers
- Principal investigators of existing awards, including:
 - NSF-funded AI institutes
 - NIH-funded AI-related projects

4 Focus Group Planning

The implementation of the survey enabled learning of community thinking and patterns around quantitative answers. However, qualitative and anecdotal answers were desired to understand the gaps between the community's described experience and practice. Thus, focus groups were planned to inform the design and development of the NAIRR portal by gathering input from various stakeholder groups with a focus on functionality, features, and design.

The focus groups were structured to include a consistent introduction to NAIRR and the discussion format, clear communication about how input would be documented, and targeted questions developed from survey results. Topics for the focus groups included:

- Topic 1: Envisioning features for the future NAIRR Portal
- Topic 2: Workforce development and training in the classroom
- Topic 3: Resource providers' perspectives
- Topic 4: Conducting research via NAIRR Portal
- Topic 5: Training and learning modalities
- Topic 6: Portal design and support

Attendees were invited from community lists, through interest forms, from survey volunteers, and at the recommendation of participating NAIRR collaborating partners. Invitees were selected to fit these profiles:

- Researchers interested in using AI resources
- Educators who might use the portal for teaching
- Resource providers who would contribute computational resources
- Support professionals who would help users navigate the system
- Workforce-development specialists

Focus groups started in October 2024 and went through January 2025. The first round of focus groups was held in person before the convening of the Gateways 2024 conference, focusing on features for the NAIRR portal and workforce development. Based on the findings from the initial focus groups, follow-up focus groups were conducted online using Zoom to facilitate group discussions. The Otter.AI service was used for capturing notes during all facilitated focus groups.

5 NAIRR Portal Workshop Planning: Applying Design Thinking

To build upon the findings from the survey and the focus groups, a workshop was planned to engage a sample of the community that would be using the NAIRR portal for AI research, using the NAIRR portal for educating the next generation of AI researchers and users, and supporting and onboarding those using services aligned with AI or providing AI resource allocations. The innovative workshop used design-thinking methodology and exercises to help participants express what the future NAIRR portal will do, identify who will use it, suggest how they will use it, and specify what must happen for it to be a helpful resource.

5.1 Design Thinking

The concept behind “design thinking” originated from an article by Peter Rowe (www.interaction-design.org). The original application of design thinking was to help architects and urban planners approach solutions, and it has evolved to be applied to the scientific and research world through adaptations by Herbert A. Simon and Richard Buchanan.

Design thinking today can be applied across multiple industries and is heavily utilized in technology planning practices to inspire, ideate, and implement solutions when challenges are complex. The design thinking process focuses on six core steps:

- *Empathize* - conduct research to develop an understanding of your users.
- *Define* - combine all your research and observe where your users’ problems exist.
- *Ideate* - generate a range of crazy and creative ideas.
- *Prototype* - build real, tactile representations for a range of ideas.
- *Test* - return to your users for feedback.
- *Implement* - put your vision into effect.

The workshop focused mainly on the ideation, prototyping, and testing processes. The empathize and define steps had been conducted before the NAIRR Portal Workshop through the community survey and focus groups. The goal of the workshop was to engage this community in focusing on the ideation, prototyping, and light “test” steps of design thinking. The exercises allowed groups to share ideas throughout the process. After the design-thinking exercises, attendees had a chance to “pitch” their ideas to the rest of the workshop attendees.

5.2 Workshop Experience

Workshop attendees were provided with a wide range of “problem statements.” These problem statements were meaningful and actionable issues that the design-thinking process would focus on solving. They were derived directly from the findings of the focus groups and survey.

At the beginning of the workshop, attendees selected a problem statement from the available options and then worked with a group of fellow attendees to step through the exercises of design thinking to generate solutions. To ensure continuity and efficiency, attendees worked within their groups for the remainder of the two days of the workshop. The set of problem statements presented to the attendees is listed in Appendix E.

Each working group reported back to all attendees after each interactive session to receive insights and feedback from the whole group.

- Day One:
 - Problem statement selection
 - Goal: Select a problem statement and work within the group to understand and empathize why it is important to the community to have it addressed.
 - Build a user archetype
 - Goal: Describe the profile and characteristics of a typical user that would be using the NAIRR Portal with a focus on the selected problem statement. Focus on what they care about most, channels of communication, and challenges to overcome.
 - Solution ideation

Cyberinfrastructure Consortium (21%), and Requesting or receiving NAIRR resource allocation for research (18%).

These results provide insights into the needs and expectations of potential NAIRR portal users, including researchers, educators, students, and industry professionals. A detailed survey report with findings is available in “Appendix A: NAIRR Pilot Portal Development Survey Summary Report,” prepared by the evaluation team led by the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC).

6.2 Focus Group Outcomes

The focus groups identified several key priorities for the portal’s development, which are outlined below.

Across all focus groups, a recurring theme was the need for **centralized and integrated access to AI resources, supporting use at all levels of expertise**. Users ranging from students to senior researchers expressed frustration with fragmented tools and inconsistent interfaces. A **unified entry point** that organizes resources by learning goals and research phases was seen as essential. Participants emphasized that **user-friendly interfaces** should be paired with **structured learning pathways**, including onboarding tutorials, guided workflows, and contextual help. For learners, especially those early in their AI journey, practical assets like **pre-configured Jupyter notebooks, reproducible benchmark datasets, and quick-start guides** were viewed as critical to fostering confidence and reducing time-to-productivity. Tailored dashboards and adaptive interfaces that respond to user skill levels were consistently recommended to support a variety of learning styles and research objectives.

The focus groups highlighted a strong demand for **centralized, trustworthy data repositories** built on **FAIR principles**. Participants stressed the importance of findability and reuse, proposing metadata scaffolding, licensing transparency, and usage metrics as standard features. Research software engineers and tool developers called for workflow tools that **streamline experimentation, model tracking, and benchmarking**. These tools should support both **GUI-based and code-driven approaches**, allowing flexibility across disciplines. Additionally, infrastructure must include support for iterative research, from prototyping to deployment. **Responsible AI** emerged as a cross-cutting concern, with users seeking features that support explainability, bias awareness, and transparency in model development. Suggestions included required disclosures during resource allocation, built-in audit trails, and integrated prompts for responsible data use and sharing.

Users consistently pointed to the need for a **paradigm shift in how computational resources are presented, improving the ease of selection and initial trials**. Instead of traditional hardware descriptions, they advocated for workflow-based categorizations aligned with user goals such as training a model, validating results, or running simulations. Participants shared that current onboarding processes for accessing resources are often overly complex. There were strong calls for more intuitive, guided allocation systems that reduce administrative burden. Several groups proposed automation tools that would allow users to trial workloads at small scale, then receive tailored resource recommendations and pre-filled allocation forms. Such features would lower the barrier to entry and minimize guesswork, especially for users unfamiliar with computing infrastructure. Enhanced transparency into resource availability and cost, along with real-time job feedback, were also noted as valuable.

A vision for the **portal as a community hub, rather than a static repository**, was shared across groups. Participants expressed interest in mentorship networks, collaborative learning spaces, and mechanisms for sharing both research and educational materials. Broader outreach to institutions and communities was identified as a critical factor in building universal access. Ideas included role-based onboarding

paths for community colleges, student-led navigator roles, and dashboards to assess and improve participation by people at different career stages over time. Certification programs, both for learners and for educators or tool contributors, were recommended to incentivize engagement and signal trust. These programs could also promote budgetary stability by formalizing pathways for user contributions and encouraging ongoing participation in training, tool development, and community building.

To summarize, key implementation priorities emerged clearly from the focus groups. First, users want improved resource discovery through intelligent search tools, metadata-rich filtering, and dynamic navigation based on research goals or user roles. Second, the need for clear, concise instructional content was emphasized across user types. Participants requested modular documentation, short walkthrough videos, proposal writing templates, and embedded help. Mechanisms for community feedback such as ratings, comments, and reproducibility tracking should be built into the platform to ensure transparency and quality control. Finally, standards for model and dataset documentation were seen as foundational to the portal's success. Participants envisioned visual trust indicators, FAIRness scores, and citation tracking systems to support reproducibility and responsible reuse across the research community.

More detailed summaries of the focus groups by topic areas are outlined in “Appendix B: Focus Group Topic Discussion Summaries.”

6.3 NAIRR Portal Workshop Outcomes

On February 4 and 5, 2025, at the San Diego Supercomputer Center, 84 participants worked within 12 groups to address focused problem statements and develop recommendations for the future portal of NAIRR. The NAIRR Workshop used the concepts defined through design thinking to ideate and prototype and then propose design ideas. For each of the 12 problem statements, participants generated and presented ideas of what the portal should be able to do (see Appendix E). The resulting insights revealed a shared ambition: to create an intelligent and frictionless environment that empowers users at all levels to engage with AI tools, datasets, and communities. The workshop elucidated recurring user archetypes, critical pain points, design priorities, and automation.

6.3.1 Understanding the People: Archetypes and Roles

A wide range of personas emerged to represent NAIRR's future users. These archetypes represent a variety of technical backgrounds, institutional contexts, and research goals. For example, *Skylar*, an AI-curious PhD student, embodies the novice researcher in need of guidance, low-barrier tools, and a safe sandbox environment. *Sam*, a graduate student in materials science, is motivated by reproducibility and impact but often overwhelmed by tool overload and poor documentation. *Postdocs and early-career Research Software Engineers (RSEs)* must juggle development timelines with publication demands, often lacking pathways for visibility and reuse of their contributions. *Inexperienced PIs* seek collaborative research management tools but are unsure how to select and trust AI platforms. Meanwhile, *educators*, both at research-intensive and teaching-focused institutions, need plug-and-play resources, curriculum validation, and integration with learning management systems.

These archetypes are not static, and they evolve, overlap, and span a continuum from undergraduate learners to domain experts and institutional decision-makers. A key outcome of the workshop was the call for *role-aware interfaces* that dynamically adapt based on user type, research task, and technical proficiency. This personalization must be reflected not only in the user interface but also in access to training, support, and relevant tools.

6.3.2 Pain Points and Design Barriers

Participants collectively identified several recurring pain points that inhibit productive engagement with AI research resources. A major barrier is onboarding friction: novice users struggle to identify the right tools, interpret allocation requirements, or even understand where to begin. This is compounded by fragmented documentation, cognitive overload from non-curated interfaces, and a lack of trust in datasets or software components.

Tool overload and permission inconsistencies were also widely reported. Users described difficulty navigating existing infrastructures due to poorly integrated services and inconsistent authentication schemes. Advanced users requested version-controlled environments and timeline visualizations, while beginners expressed a need for explainable, phased walkthroughs that build confidence.

Educators and under-resourced institutions face additional barriers, such as limited access to curated curricula, lack of validation mechanisms, and bandwidth constraints. Workshop participants emphasized the importance of the design with specific modes, support structures, and visibility for users from MSIs, community colleges, and underserved institutions.

6.3.3 Design Outcomes: Toward a Flexible and Trustworthy Portal

To address these pain points, participants co-developed paper prototypes reflecting solutions across user support, AI tooling, training, collaboration, and governance. Participants desired clarity for the personalized user journeys within the NAIRR Portal, beginning with a centralized dashboard that orients users to relevant tools, collaborators, and projects. Suggestions included skill-based badge systems that adapt visible content based on proficiency, and wizard-like interfaces that guide users through “identify → learn → launch” paths.

For novice researchers, multiple teams proposed a 10-minute-to-first-use experience enabled by sandbox environments, curated workflows, and Google-like search with explainable AI. These designs would help users experiment, build confidence, and transition into more complex computational settings.

To support advanced users and developers, prototypes emphasized tool development pipelines featuring GUI/API hybrids, reusable templates, trust signals like “FAIRness scores,” and publishing-readiness checklists. Integration with version control, metadata tagging, and dataset reproducibility ratings was proposed to encourage broader tool reuse and citation.

Training and education were also central themes. Several groups proposed curriculum hubs where educators could access validated, peer-rated content, reusable assignments, and walk-throughs of AI models. Learning Management System integration and role-specific interfaces—for example, sandboxing for adjuncts vs. custom modules for faculty—would reduce the time needed to adopt AI in classrooms.

Collaboration tool prototypes were designed with transparency and trust at their core. Researcher matchmaking based on profiles (e.g., Google Scholar, ORCID), version-controlled syllabus exchanges, and grant-ready project templates were suggested. Social features such as Slack-like chat, opt-in mentoring, and visibility into institutional readiness reinforce the idea of the portal as a community-builder, not just a service aggregator.

6.3.4 Automation and Intelligence

Participants envisioned AI-powered assistants throughout the portal experience. These include chatbots for tool recommendations, proposal drafting, resource selection, and dataset discovery, many using knowledge graphs linking publications, tools, and models. Importantly, teams emphasized the need for explainability, user privacy, and domain sensitivity in these AI agents.

One team proposed a FAIRness Assistant chatbot to guide users in improving dataset documentation and reuse potential, issuing visibility badges based on compliance levels. Another designed a Responsible Resource Access System, which unlocks high-sensitivity tools only after completing training modules. These ideas highlight the community's prioritization of responsible AI development, transparency, and reproducibility.

Prototypes also incorporated gamified learning and training discovery tools, offering leaderboards, social integration, and skill tracking across internal and external platforms. These features, combined with visual dashboards and role-sensitive filters, would help users progress along learning pathways and stay engaged over time.

At the end of the workshop we asked the following four questions.

- What are the most important next steps for NAIRR from your perspective?
- How can we keep this momentum going beyond today?
- What is one immediate action you or your organization can take to support NAIRR?
- What does success for NAIRR look like to you in the next 3-5 years?

The answers were mostly around strategic funding and long-term vision, emphasizing user experience and researcher engagement, and need for better mechanisms for sharing AI-related data sets.

Conclusion: Exemplar Portal Recommendations

Based on the extensive community engagement from the survey, focus groups, and workshop, the following exemplar features are recommended to inform the NAIRR portal's ongoing development. These recommendations reflect both immediate user needs and long-term strategic goals.

- **AI-Powered Assistance:** This includes incorporating intelligent support tools such as chatbots, guided onboarding, and personalized recommendations to help users navigate resources, identify relevant tools and data, and streamline access to computing and training assets. Workshop participants emphasized the need for intelligent systems to guide users through the complex NAIRR environment. One design concept proposed an AI-powered recommender system to help users learn new tools and methodologies, discover relevant resources, and receive tailored training suggestions. Implementation pathways could include deploying context-aware chatbots to assist users in navigating the portal and completing everyday tasks, such as resource allocation and training selection. Additionally, utilizing machine learning (ML) techniques provides personalized content recommendations based on user behavior profiles and project needs. Furthermore, integrating a conversational AI interface would support onboarding and reduce the learning curve, especially for first-time users.
- **Community Engagement:** Both the survey respondents and focus groups had a strong interest in building a collaborative and community-driven platform. Suggestions included supporting communication for users across organizations, creating shared project spaces, and enabling users to exchange ideas, code, and feedback. This can be implemented through various mechanisms, such as creating user profiles with badges and leaderboards to encourage participation and recognize contributions, launching expert networks and mentoring programs to connect new users with experienced researchers, and introducing light gamification methods and collaborative events to drive engagement.
- **Streamlined Resource Discovery:** Survey respondents identified that resource discovery tools (31%) and data management tools (29%) were the top priorities for portal interface enhancements. Focus groups proposed features such as faceted navigation, guided resource

selection, and a dashboard tailored to specific use cases, including those for educators, postdocs, and others. These can be integrated by creating features such as innovative search tools and knowledge graphs to help users discover datasets, tools, and training materials aligned with their research goals. The portal can offer a FAIR-aligned data registry with filters for data type, format, licensing, and provenance. Lastly, the portal could provide a visual, task-based discovery workflow for typical user personas, such as “find a dataset for my model” or “launch a template Jupyter Notebook for training.”

- **Transparent AI Use:** Focus group discussions emphasized the need for transparency and trust in the origins of data and models. Mechanisms for implementation can embed tooltips and provenance tags throughout datasets and models to inform users about fairness, bias, and compliance. Furthermore, the portal can have a designated area with curated AI training resources, compliance checklists, and case studies. The portal can also explore offering a “FAIRness” dashboard and badges to reflect the reproducible use of shared research assets.
- **Bridging the Resource Gap:** Many workshop teams focused on the unique needs of under-resourced or early-career users. The designs for postdocs emphasized “job builder” tools, metadata-driven data search and selection, and simplified automation of workflows. These can be implemented by providing low-barrier entry points for new users to AI and cyberinfrastructure (CI). This includes curating starter kits and tutorials based on research roles. Furthermore, modular workflows can be developed with drag-and-drop job builders that abstract complexity. Lastly, the portal could implement mentor-guided walkthroughs and use-case templates for common research needs such as image analysis or LLM fine-tuning.

NAIRR Pilot

National Artificial Intelligence
Research Resource Pilot

NSF Center of Excellence in Cyberinfrastructure: SGX3
NSF NAIRR Supplement

NAIRR Portal Development Survey Summary Report
February 28, 2025

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I. Introduction

Project Overview

The National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource (NAIRR) Pilot is a proof-of-concept for a national research infrastructure to support innovative, AI-enabled research and education. The pilot is being funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) in partnership with 12 other federal agencies and 26 non-governmental partners, and it will run from January 2024 to January 2026 before transitioning to a full NAIRR implementation. According to the NAIRR Task Force Report published in 2023, the NAIRR portal is a key component of the NAIRR that will integrate computing, data, and training resources to support open AI research and research that uses AI. The NSF-funded SGX3 Center of Excellence for Science Gateways has led the effort to provide the NAIRR Pilot portal and to design the NAIRR portal. The NSF NAIRR Supplement project entitled, “Community Discovery for Near-Term NAIRR Pilot portal Functionality,” is an effort to engage a wide variety of stakeholders to provide feedback and guide the next phases of the pilot portal as it grows from being NSF-focused to community-driven and sets the stage for the NAIRR portal.

The **project goals** are as follows:

1. Determine short-term capabilities for the portal that can serve the community in the next 3 years, as well as a longer-term view of how the portal can serve the NAIRR community during the next 5-10 years.
2. Culminate with a recommendation for phased implementation of portal capabilities in the NAIRR Pilot portal and the design of the NAIRR portal following the pilot phase.
3. Develop functionalities to enable better engagement with users of NAIRR Pilot resources, including implementation of support and communications features to engage the community.
4. Develop and deploy new visualizations that showcase NAIRR Pilot investments and activities.
5. Fulfill other community enhancements that may arise as the NAIRR Pilot progresses such as integration of NAIRR demo projects.

Data Collection Overview

Beginning in Fall 2024, SGX3 partnered with The University of Texas at Austin (UT Austin) Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) Evaluation Services team to collaborate on the data collection, analysis, and reporting for the NAIRR supplement project. The SGX3 and TACC evaluation team are using a mixed methods approach to assess community needs and provide formative data to guide short- and long-term portal development. The **guiding questions** are as follows:

- User needs and expectations: What are the needs and expectations of potential NAIRR portal users, including researchers, educators, students, and industry professionals?
- Portal features and functionality: What features and functionalities should be included in the NAIRR portal, such as data management tools, collaboration platforms, and educational resources?
- AI-related research activities: What AI-related research activities are stakeholders currently engaged in, and how can the NAIRR portal support these activities and activities that are envisioned for the future?
- Education and training: What educational resources and training programs should be offered through the NAIRR portal?
- Governance: What are stakeholders’ perspectives on governance in AI research, and how can the NAIRR portal promote responsible AI development and use?

The SGX3 team and TACC evaluators thoroughly reviewed the NAIRR Task Force Report to develop the **NAIRR Portal Development Survey**. The survey uses both closed- and open-ended items to understand

NAIRR Pilot portal users' and potential NAIRR portal users' AI-related research activities; needs for portal features, functionalities, and resources; feedback on the interface design; and expectations of governance in AI research. Prior to the full administration of the survey, it was pilot tested with a small group of select stakeholders and revised based on their feedback.

The refined survey was administered online to a wide variety of stakeholders via Qualtrics from October 2, 2024 through January 2, 2025. **Anonymous survey** links were distributed through SGX3 Slack Workspace channels and community partners (e.g., Statewide California Earthquake Center (SCEC) community, Massachusetts Green HPC (MGHPCC)). **Direct emails** to request survey participation were sent to the following **stakeholder groups**:

- Subscribers to the SGX3 mailing list (links sent to approximately 1,700 SGX3 subscribers)
- Members of the NAIRR Pilot portal user list, including (links sent to approximately 200 NAIRR users):
 - Authors of the NAIRR Task Force Report
 - Recipients of NAIRR Pilot resource allocations
 - Representatives of NAIRR Pilot resources providers
- Principal investigators (PIs) of existing awards, including:
 - NSF-funded AI institutes (links sent to approximately 13,000 PIs)
 - NIH-funded AI-related projects (links sent to approximately 41,000 PIs)

This report summarizes the NAIRR Portal Development Survey findings. Using preliminary survey findings, the SGX3 team conducted focus groups and a workshop to garner portal development support and to gather additional feedback from the community. Findings from the focus groups and workshop will be provided in the full NAIRR Portal Report that will also include the survey findings shared in this report.

II. NAIRR Portal Development Survey Findings

Participant Profile

A total of 1,234 responses were collected for the NAIRR Portal Development Survey that was administered online from Oct 2, 2024 to Jan 2, 2025. Among all respondents, 177 only provided background information and were excluded from the analyses; resulting in a final total of 1,057 responses included in this report.

Participants' Institution

Nearly all (96%) respondents are affiliated with a US-based institution, and most (78%) represent doctoral universities (see **Figure 1**). Small proportions (<1-4%) of respondents represent master's colleges and universities, baccalaureate/associate's colleges, federally funded research and development centers (FFRDCs), commercial research and development (R&D) operations, special focus institutions, and tribal colleges and universities. Some (6%) respondents specified other institution types including medical centers or schools, government, and non-profit or private research centers.

Figure 1. Institution Type (N=1057)

Participant Background

Figure 2 shows that almost two-thirds (64%) of respondents were faculty members. Other respondents included researchers (11%), administrators (6%), research software engineers (6%), graduate students (3%), other college/university staff (3%), postdoctoral fellows (2%), instructors/teachers (1%), and undergraduate students (<1%). A small percentage (4%) of respondents reported other roles not listed as options, including management roles, directors, librarians, consultant, and “RCD professionals.”

Figure 2. Professional Role (N=1057)

Most respondents are primarily involved with research in the biological sciences (22%), health sciences (18%), or computer and information sciences (14%; see **Figure 3**). The large number of survey invitations sent to NIH PIs may explain why biological and health sciences are the most common research areas among respondents. Other (5-7%) respondents reported their primary area of research as being in the physical and mathematical sciences, social sciences, or life sciences. Fewer (<1-4%) respondents selected cyberinfrastructure (CI), data sciences, environmental science, statistics, arts and humanities, or

professional disciplines. Most respondents who selected “Other” for this question specified a sub-field (e.g., “psychology”, “marine geology,” “oncology”), indicated they conduct multidisciplinary research (e.g., “data science + environmental science”), or mentioned education broadly or with a domain area (e.g., “math education,” “tech education”). Some respondents explained they are not directly involved in any research.

Figure 3. Primary Area of Research (N=1057)

AI Experiences and NAIRR Engagement

When respondents were asked to rate their current levels of AI/ML expertise on a scale from unaware to expert, 30% self-identified as aware of the uses of AI/ML, 32% as knowledgeable, 21% as proficient, 15% as expert, and 3% were unaware of AI/ML applications (see **Figure 4**). As **Figure 5** shows, half (50%) of respondents were using AI/ML, more than one third (37%) were aware of AI/ML applications, less than one quarter (24%) create/build AI/ML, and some (12%) extend AI/ML. The remaining (3%) respondents were unaware of AI/ML.

Figure 4. Extent of AI/ML Expertise (N=1057)

Figure 5. Extent of AI/ML Experience (N=1057)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

As shown in **Figure 6**, most (80%) respondents are not currently engaged with NAIRR. Some respondents who are engaged with NAIRR request or receive NAIRR resource allocations for research (11%) and/or for education and teaching (4%). Small proportions (1-3%) of respondents represent an existing NSF AI Institute award or efforts known to the Minority Serving Cyberinfrastructure Consortium and/or identified as NAIRR resource providers, a member of the SGX3 AI Blueprint Factory, or as an author of a the NAIRR Task Force Report. A few (3%) respondents were unsure of their connection or affiliation with NAIRR or noted that they support related projects but are not themselves directly engaged with NAIRR. The project uptake was still in progress at the time of the survey administration, which may explain why most respondents were not engaged with or even aware of NAIRR prior to administration of the survey.

Figure 6. NAIRR Engagement (N=1057)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Almost half (45%) of respondents currently use open-source pre-trained models, and over one third (37%) use models to be trained (see **Figure 7**). Others use proprietary pre-trained models (28%) or open-weight pre-trained models (18%). The few (2%) respondents who selected “Other” in response to this item clarified that they used AI/ML models that were discipline specific, created by respondents their teams, or a combination of models offered for selection in this question. One quarter (25%) are not presently using any AI/ML software tool environments.

Figure 7. Current AI/ML Models (N=1057)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Almost half (41-44%) of respondents described their AI-related research activities as concerning software/algorithm creation and/or data production, and about one fifth (21%) indicated their activities were concerning building CI (see **Figure 8**). Some (7%) respondents described “Other” activities, including to scientific and other communities, use within and supporting experimental applications, and text editing. More than one quarter (27%) of respondents are not using AI for research.

Figure 8. Respondents' AI-Related Research Activities (N=1057)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

More than half (55%) of respondents use machine learning in research (see **Figure 9**). About one third (32-36%) use neural networks, deep learning, and natural language processing. Less than one fifth (12-17%) use computer vision, reinforcement learning, or AI-driven experimental design. Respondents who selected “Other” clarified specific types of AI resources they use in their work (e.g., “LLMs” or “generative AI”), the type of work with which they engage (e.g., “legal implications”), or that they do not understand the differences between response options. More than one quarter (27%) are not using AI for research.

Figure 9. AI Types Respondents Use in Research (N=1057)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

NAIRR Portal Usage and Features

General Purposes

For almost three fourths (74%) of respondents, using the NAIRR portal for research would be *very* or *extremely important* (see **Figure 10**). The majority (51-62%) indicated that using the portal for computing resources, computational tools, data sharing, curating, or management, training and documentation, AI model sharing, education, inference for AI models, and to deploy AI application would be *very* or *extremely important*. For less than half (38-48%) of respondents, user community cross-collaboration, user support and tickets, and publishing outcomes would be *very* or *extremely important* purposes for using the portal. Less than one third (30-31%) of respondents indicated that allocation management and NAIRR news and events would be *very* or *extremely important* purposes for using the portal. Finally, 169 respondents added purposes that were not included in the options, and less than one third (30%) of those respondents indicated that their additions are *very* or *extremely important*. These specific additions included “competitions,” and “help desk.”

Figure 10. Purpose(s) Respondents Would Use the Portal (N=754)

As shown in **Figure 11**, two thirds (67%) of respondents indicated that supporting collaborations across NAIRR portal users is *moderately* or *very important*.

Figure 11. Importance of Supporting Collaborations Across Portal (N=754)

The majority (62%) of respondents indicated they would like to see Jupyter integrated into the NAIRR portal (see **Figure 12**). Approximately half (44-56%) are interested in the integration of PyTorch, RStudio, and/or TensorFlow. A smaller proportion (8-15%) of respondents would like to see JAX, Quarto, and “Other” tools such as AlphaFold2, MATLAB, ArcGIS, and ilastik integrated.

Figure 12. AI Tools or Software Wanted in the Portal (N=754)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Computing

Over two thirds (69%) of respondents conduct their computational work from a personal or company-issued computer, almost half (46-48%) use resources from their research group and/or campus research computing facilities, and less than one fifth (10-18%) use commercial or federally funded cloud computing and/or ACCESS (Advanced CI Coordination Ecosystem: Services and Support) (see **Figure 13**). A small proportion (1-8%) of respondents currently conduct their computational work through science gateways, at university-based or government national labs, through distributed infrastructures, at industry labs, or via other resources (e.g., cloud computing services, TACC, Tribal Networks).

Figure 13. Where Respondents Currently Conduct Computational Work (N=740)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Respondents who indicated how they conduct computational work (see **Figure 13**) were asked what methods they prefer for using or requesting computational allocations. As shown in **Figure 14**, the majority (64%) of respondents prefer on-campus resources (e.g., campus credits, local campus resources), for using or requesting computational allocations. Almost one third (29-31%) prefer requestable program allocations (e.g., NSF ACCESS, DOE INCITE, NIH STRIDES) or paying for a subscription (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud, Azure Cloud). Almost half (46%) of respondents own their own computation resources.

Figure 14. Preferred Methods for Using/Requesting Allocations (N=683)*

* Respondents could select all that apply; question not displayed to respondents who do not conduct computational work

Almost half to half (43-50%) of respondents indicated that interactive, API, and/or batch computing modalities are needed in the NAIRR portal (see **Figure 15**). More than one third (37%) were not sure what modalities are needed. Respondents who selected “Other” noted “all modalities,” “peer-to-peer sharing,” and “access to storage and cloud computing as [needed].” Regarding computational job capabilities, almost half (47-49%) of respondents indicated that batch processing and Jupyter notebooks are needed (see **Figure 16**). More than one-third (35-39%) indicated their needs for API access and job monitoring and reporting. Less than one third (29-32%) of respondents need containerized applications and workflow management. About one quarter (24%) need custom web applications. Some respondents added “Other” additional computational job capabilities including “image analysis,” “accounting,” and “building AI tools with prompt engineering.”

Figure 15. Computing Modalities Needed in the Portal (N=722)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Figure 16. Computational Job Capabilities Needed in the Portal (N=725)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Education

More than half (51%) of respondents teach content in their domain area (see **Figure 17**). Less than half (38-40%) teach research methodology and/or technical skills related to using software or tools. Less than a quarter (20%) teach technical skills for software or tool development. A few (1%) respondents indicated they teach in “Other” areas, including “software preservation,” “carpentries,” “technical skills related to writing,” “computational chemistry,” and “on-demand training.” Almost one third (30%) indicated they do not teach or host any course, training, or workshop in the listed areas; these respondents were not asked subsequent questions about their instruction.

Figure 17. Areas in Which Respondents Teach (N=682)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Figure 18 shows that more than one third (34-45%) of respondents use AI in their instruction to apply AI, develop course materials, and address AI-related issues. Approximately one quarter (19-26%) develop AI models, account for the limitations of AI, use standard AI-ready datasets, assess the quality of AI models, and use course-specific AI datasets. Some (5%) respondents described “Other” ways they incorporate AI in their classrooms. For example, they use AI tools to support course tasks such as grading or vocabulary expansion, or they address AI conceptually but not practically in their courses. Approximately one quarter (24%) of respondents do not use AI/ML resources in their instruction at all.

Figure 18. How Respondents Use AI in Their Instruction (N=478)*

* Respondents could select all that apply, Question not displayed to respondents who do not teach

As **Figure 19** shows, a slight majority (51%) of respondents use Jupyter notebooks in instruction. Approximately one third (32%) use commercial cloud tools (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud) and one quarter (26%) use Docker, Singularity, and other container tools. Less (10-15%) respondents use the following: academic cloud tools (e.g. Jetstream, Open Science Grid), ACCESS or federal allocations, science gateways (e.g., Tapis, HUBzero, Galazy), and Kubernetes. Ten percent of respondents specified “Other” software and training resources that were not included in the options, including tools like “SPSS,” “AlphaFold2,”

“GitHub,” and “options publicly available to students.” Just under one quarter (24%) do not use software or training resources in their instruction.

Figure 19. Software and Training Resources Respondents Use in Instruction (N=478)*

* Respondents could select all that apply, Question not displayed to respondents who do not teach

As shown in **Figure 20**, approximately three quarters (76%) of respondents indicated that education and training tools would be *very* to *extremely* valuable to include in the NAIRR portal.

Figure 20. Value of Portal Including Education and Training Tools* (N=458)

* Question not displayed to respondents who do not teach

Data Management

As shown in **Figure 21**, the majority (51-64%) of respondents indicated that data analysis, data sharing, and data storage are data management features that are needed in the NAIRR portal. Less than half (42-47%) requested data downloading and data publishing. Less than one third (27-28%) need data versioning and data staging. Four percent (4%) added “Other” data management features, including data visualization, validation, integration, and verification. Fourteen percent of respondents do not plan to use any data management features.

Figure 21. Data Management Features Needed in the Portal (N=671)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Regarding data transfer capabilities, more than half (51%, see **Figure 22**) of respondents indicated that data sharing service is needed in the NAIRR portal. Under half (40%) need cloud storage and about one quarter to one third (23-30%) need a web server, SFTP/CP, and Globus. Less than one fifth (19%) of respondents are not sure. One tenth (10%) of respondents do not anticipate using data transfer capabilities with the NAIRR portal, and a few (2%) added data transfer capabilities that were not included in the options, including “Tapis” and “Amazon Web Services (AWS).”

Figure 22. Data Transfer Capabilities Needed in the Portal (N=666)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Most (81%) respondents indicated that providing private, community, and/or public data sharing is at least *moderately important*, with almost two thirds (63%) of respondents indicating providing this is *very to extremely important* (see **Figure 23**).

Figure 23. Importance of Portal Providing Ability for Private, Community, and/or Public Data Sharing (N=666)

Most (82%) respondents also indicated that providing management and/or access to regulated data is at least *moderately important*; in this case, about half (52%) of respondents indicated providing this is *very to extremely important* (see **Figure 24**).

Figure 24. Importance of Portal Providing Management and/or Access to Regulated Data (N=663)

Design and User Interface

As shown in **Figure 25**, more than one third of respondents currently use portal/scientific gateways in research or instruction (34%) or do not currently use them but would like to in the future (38%). Fewer respondents do not currently use portals/scientific gateways and do not plan to in the future (13%) or are not sure (16%).

Figure 25. Whether Respondents Use Portals/Scientific Gateways in Research or Instruction (N=661)

When respondents were asked which functionalities should be prioritized in the NAIRR portal design, almost one third (31%) selected data management tools (see **Figure 26**). Approximately one fourth (22-25%) selected each of the following: resource discovery tools, user guides, collaboration platforms, and job submission interface. A smaller proportion (16%) selected publication features, and three percent specified “Other” functionalities that were not included in the options, like “large language models” and “allocation viewing and management.”

Figure 26. Functionalities to be Prioritized in the Portal Design (N=661)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Support and Training

As shown in **Figure 27**, the majority (56-57%) of respondents would like to develop skills and knowledge around machine learning and data analysis. Less than half (37-46%) would like to develop skills and knowledge around deep learning, using AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT), AI model evaluation and interpretation, data processing and management, and neural networks. Approximately one third (30-34%) selected natural language processing (NLP), AI-driven experimental design, and programming languages. Less than one fourth (21-23%) selected reinforcement learning or computer vision. A few (4%) respondents added “Other” AI skills and knowledge, including “NeuroAI applications,” and “data driven astronomy.”

Figure 27. AI Skills/Knowledge Respondents Want to Develop (N=656)

* Respondents could select all that apply

Two thirds (67%) of respondents typically learn technical skills by reading documentation. The majority (56-62%) learn through web search, online courses, and hands-on tutorials (see **Figure 28**). Less than half (34-43%) use YouTube and approximately one third take in-person courses. Less than one quarter (18-21%) leverage conference tutorials and Chatbots, such as ChatGPT. Four percent added “Other” ways of learning including “engaging with peers or mentors,” “independently practicing skills,” and “reading books or papers.”

Figure 28. How Respondents Typically Learn Technical Skills (N=656)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

More than three quarters (78%) of respondents mentor graduate students, more than two thirds (69%) mentor undergraduate students, and more than half (58%) mentor post-docs or post-graduate students (see **Figure 29**). Less than one quarter (18-20%) mentor high school students and REU students. Some (8%) respondents do not mentor others and three percent mentor “medical students,” “junior faculty,” “working professionals,” and “teachers.”

Figure 29. Types of Students that Respondents Mentor (N=656)*

* Respondents could select all that apply

Ensuring Institutional Access

To ensure access to NAIRR resources across geographic and institutional backgrounds, nearly two thirds (64%) of respondents expressed support for outreach to geographic and institutional communities (see **Figure 30**). Less than half (41-47%) selected each of the following: design and language support, flexible access models/responsive design, tailored training, and monitoring and feedback. Fewer respondents were either not sure (12%), indicated that no action is needed (2%), or suggested “Other” steps (5%) such as “including a range of institutions,” “[tracking] who is using the portal,” and “[making] things accessible for non-experts.”

Figure 30. Steps to Ensure Institutional Access to Resources (N=650)

* Respondents could select all that apply

Anticipated Impact

More than two thirds (67%, see **Figure 31**) of respondents anticipated access to AI and/or NAIRR portal resources would *moderately to extensively* increase their effectiveness as an instructor and/or their research productivity. Some respondents did not think it would increase their effectiveness/productivity (4%) or were unsure (15%) regarding the impact.

Figure 31. Anticipated Increase in Instructor Effectiveness and/or Research Productivity Based on Access to AI/NAIRR Portal (N=649)

Additional Feedback

How would AI help you transform your data into knowledge that can be taught in a current or future classroom or training environment? (N=670)

- **Unsure (22%):** “Not sure, but I know it’s very important to my students” and “I have no idea. I don’t really understand what AI can do.”
- **Data collection, organization, and analysis (16%):** “Allow [for] quicker data processing,” “AI can find relationships between the data that are not clearly understandable via traditional linear and no-linear models,” and “Facilitate the easy analysis of data in a single platform. Right now, resources, data, and analysis are distributed.”

- **Support teaching and learning** (14%): “Creation of course content and hands-on experience,” “Personalized learning, real-time feedback, and data-driven improvements,” and “Having a virtual assistant that helps teach students by guiding them through the material.”
- **Generate content, materials, and code** (13%): “Content generation,” “By translating my requests into computer-understandable code,” and “Creating activities using a data set [and] allowing students to use datasets in an introductory class with prompts instead of having to first develop a deeper set of computational skills.”
- **Not applicable** (13%): “N/A,” “I am not currently teaching,” and “I don’t believe [AI] can do this with subjective, sociocultural data.”
- **Use in research/publishing** (6%): “Training AI for research,” “Improve [the] execution of experiments,” and “I teach students to understand AI and use AI in their research.”
- **Developing/using models** (6%): “Developing models,” “Teaching how to create prediction models for environmental research,” and “I am working on creating AI models that understand the content of datasets to help non-programmers get started with generated source code that will solve their issues by using plain-text prompts.”
- **Training and support** (5%): “Learning new skills,” “Allow trainees to discover new topics or solutions for niche disciplines on their own,” and “Open, efficient access to larger, non-toy datasets would support curriculum for training and education on more advanced topics.”
- **Other** (Less than 5% per theme): “Manage workflow,” “As an applied data scientist, I am intensely concerned about how rapidly ‘AI’ is being developed without protections,” and “AI can help make data more accessible by creating a natural language interface to query and explore the data, allowing for democratization of access to complex information.”

“AI could help transform complex oceanographic data into accessible visualizations and interactive models that demonstrate impacts on marine ecosystems, enabling students to explore real-world environmental data while learning about ocean biogeochemistry and carbon cycling dynamics.”

- Survey respondent

“[I] would like to be able to use AI to optimize basic science research and translational medicine to enhance capabilities and learn technical skills.”

- Survey respondent

What recommendations do you have for the NAIRR portal to evolve over time and continue meeting the needs of the education and research community? (N=301)

- **N/A, none, or unsure** (24%): “N/A,” “I don’t have any specific recommendations,” and “I am not familiar with the program, so if the outreach team could tell me how my research could benefit from it that would be helpful.”
- **Request/use feedback** (22%): “Keep reaching out for feedback before, during, and after implementation,” “Surveys and advisory boards will be important to keep in touch with the needs of the many communities you will serve,” and “Regularly access usage and seek feedback to understand who is using [the portal] and why, as well as whether and who [else] might benefit from using [it] but is not.”

“Prioritize user-driven evolution by gathering feedback from educators and researchers to address emerging needs.”
- Survey respondent
- **Ensure accessibility/awareness of portal resources** (12%): “Provide resources that let under-resourced labs get started on core tasks quickly with rapid feedback to know if they are succeeding” and “There should be much more concerted effort to develop ways to raise awareness and excite HBCU students about the impact and opportunities from the imminent AI revolution so that they can be prepared as much as students in other institutions.”

“The largest barrier to using AI I have seen is the technical leap to understanding how AI systems need to be created and used. If NAIRR can continually lower that barrier to entry, it will better meet the needs of the education and research community.”
- Survey respondent

- **Communication/outreach/collaboration** (10%): “More outreach about what NAIRR is trying to achieve,” “Outreach and communication to users and universities to promote the platform will be important,” and “Fostering partnerships with academic and industry leaders will help provide valuable tools, data, and opportunities for collaborative innovation.”
 - **Stay up to date with trends and resources** (8%): “Stay relevant,” “[Update] content to reflect state-of-the-art practices,” and “As AI is quickly evolving, the portal will need to stay on top of trends and developments in AI methods and advances.”
 - **Project pacing/focus** (8%): “Incremental approach is needed,” “NAIRR needs clarification on whether it is a research or an education platform,” and “NAIRR should decide its focus. Is this primarily a resource for have-nots, or is it a resource that operates at a scale beyond what a typical R1 campus could possibly provide?”
 - **Provide training/workshops/conferences** (8%): “Provide workshops with examples,” “Have guides explaining AI uses to non-computational scientists,” and “Have convenings around the rapid innovation coming with AI and how it is affecting corporations, educational institutions, and government.”
- “[Provide] learning material [that is] able to guide learners from the very start to the more intermediate and advanced [levels].”
- Survey respondent
- **Portal design** (7%): “Prioritize functionality over visual appeal,” “Implement chat-based support and online feedback that opens a ticket with each submission,” and “The most important thing is to allow users to discover resources easily, request allocation, get allocation efficiently, and have good user support.”
 - **Consider needs of various stakeholders** (6%): “Listen to a range of users, including beginners to advanced research developers” and “Ensuring there is proper representation from both public, private, and nonprofit sectors in the steering committee and subcommittees [is] a good start, but also providing avenues to receive solicitation from the community.”
 - **Welcome users from different backgrounds** (4%): “Remember that the community is not primarily NIH-funded labs or institutions,” “Be open to listening to the unheard voices,” and “Please work with MSI [or] HSI institutions. They lack the infrastructure and need to be able to help train students in [machine learning and] AI.”
 - **Other** (Less than 5% per theme): “Provide funding opportunities for research using NAIRR,” “Review and emulate leading AI-focused portals such as HuggingFace and GitHub Copilot,” “Clarify the security models in place or planned and how to limit or mitigate vulnerabilities,” and “I’m concerned that NAIRR will not have enough funding to realize the vision originally outlined.”

If you had a vision for a NAIRR portal that hasn’t been addressed by the questions above, what would it be? (N=224)

- **N/A, none, or unsure** (46%): “N/A,” “Nothing I can think of,” and “No additional comments.”
 - **Data use and management** (8%): “Standardization of data,” “Access to large amounts of healthcare data that is deidentified,” and “The NAIRR portal must ensure a consistent, comprehensive infrastructure that connects all data resources seamlessly.”
 - **Ease of use** (8%): “Ease of use,” “Lower barrier of entry for new users,” and “More emphasis on beginners so that students coming with less training have some hope of getting a foot in the door.”
 - **Project goals/purpose** (7%): “I would prefer it to be excellent in few aspects up front rather than being able
- “NAIRR could target university student groups to provide training, resources, and ways of using NAIRR.”
- Survey respondent

to do everything,” “It is crucial to be able to host, train, and fine-tune extremely large models so that these do not exist only inside large tech companies,” and “I would hope that the portal meets the needs of a research community on their terms, without imagining, for example, a drift in research attention into domains that are easier to commercialize.”

- **Training, tutorials, and guides** (7%): “Availability of precision tutoring,” “All faculty, staff, and students have access to AI computing training and infrastructure,” and “It would feature an AI practices lab with real-world scenarios and decision-making exercises to deepen understanding.”
- **Portal design/UX** (5%): “Design simplicity,” “Interactive tool to create customized views of data,” and “The single biggest frustration is when you can’t find what you are looking for on a user interface quickly. Have an expert in user experience on the team who can help in basic design of the NAIRR portal from the beginning.”
- **Data sharing and collaboration** (5%): “My vision is to anticipate a shared national research infrastructure for responsible discovery and innovation in AI” and “I think it could be a place where AI scientists come to look for datasets to support novel AI architectures, as well as domain expertise to coproduce new AI together with domain experts.”
- **Other** (Less than 5% per theme): “Domain specific and interdisciplinary working groups to enable collaborative research leveraging NAIRR,” “Check out [HuggingFace] for more insight; [this] could perhaps aid in the development of this portal,” “To allow all students [to have] open access to current research tools used by practitioners,” and “Make AI for everyone. Make a platform that can help people from [different] languages and locations.”

“I am curious how the portal envisions the engagement of users that are at different stages of their understanding of needs and available tools, how the portal plans to serve this audience of a wide range of needs.”

- Survey respondent

Please use the space below to share additional comments or suggestions. (N=106)

- **Positive comment** (39%): “Great initiative,” “This is an exciting initiative,” and “I actively use CloudBank, [but] a more powerful computing and data infrastructure is very exciting and would accelerate my research.”
- **N/A or none** (32%): “N/A” and “No additional comments.”
- **Clarifying responses or role** (11%): “I didn’t know what many of the questions were talking about,” “I am not sure I can be a good subject for your focus groups, given how little I have used [AI],” and “I am an Associate Dean for Research in addition to being a faculty member, so I tried to answer these for my research community not just myself.”
- **Project purpose, direction, or impact** (8%): “Having a hard time seeing how this competes with industry,” “Think big, then figure out a continuing series of small steps to reach the larger vision over time,” and “Need NAIRR to be useful for biomedical applications, which means it must be privacy-preserving in data acquisition, data storage, [and] analytics.”
- **Other** (Less than 5% of responses): “Make accessibility more affordable by developing a more user-friendly interface with intuitive navigation and search capabilities”

“The development of a national SGX3 portal is an essential step in expanding educational resources to society, and vital to enabling the continuing learning process [that is] so essential.”

- Survey respondent

III. Summary

This report shares findings from the Fall 2024 administration of the NAIRR Portal Development Survey. A total of 1,057 participants responded to at least part of the survey and are included in the analyses. The majority of respondents are faculty members. Most were affiliated with doctoral universities and about one-third were from MSIs. Respondents represented a wide range of research areas, including biological sciences, health sciences, and computer and information sciences. Most respondents were not engaged with NAIRR.

According to a subset of 754 respondents, the most important reasons to use NAIRR are research, computing resources and tools, and data sharing, curating, or management. Many respondents also highlighted the importance of supporting project collaborations across NAIRR portal users. Regarding AI tools or software, respondents would like to use Jupyter and PyTorch in the NAIRR portal. The majority of respondents currently conduct their computational work on personal or company-issued computers and would prefer a free on-demand allocation method. More than two thirds of respondents teach in some capacity and almost half apply AI in their instruction, particularly using Jupyter notebooks. Respondents would value having education and training tools in the NAIRR portal.

Regarding data management, many respondents would use the NAIRR portal for data analysis, data sharing, and data storage. Similarly, they want the NAIRR portal to include a data sharing service. Respondents hope to develop skills in machine learning and data analysis and currently do so by reading documentation, conducting web searches, and completing online courses and hands-on tutorials. Most respondents currently mentor graduate students, undergraduate students, and/or post-docs or post-graduates. Respondents placed importance on AI research practices and guidelines, and recommended outreach to geographic and institutional communities to ensure access to resources. Respondents were mixed regarding the impact of the NAIRR portal could have on their teaching effectiveness or research productivity.

Respondents anticipated using AI to help transform their data through improved data collection, organization, and analysis techniques; to support classroom and professional teaching and learning; and to generate classroom materials, content, or code. They shared a range of opinions about the importance of the NAIRR portal to address AI research practices, including guidelines are integral to AI research and use, as well as considerations that practices are already provided elsewhere. Respondents also shared specific concerns about data privacy and sovereignty and the lack of awareness of practice by some AI users.

Recommendations for the NAIRR portal to evolve over time included incorporating and being responsive to feedback mechanisms (e.g., through surveys, reviewing usage data, and engaging users directly), ensuring ease of access to and awareness of NAIRR portal resources (e.g., offering trainings on portal use and applications, prioritizing ease of use when developing the portal design), fostering partnerships with stakeholders (e.g., universities, industry), and considering the needs of a wide-range of users. Respondents expressed a need for clarification on the NAIRR portal's purpose, including to whom the portal would be accessible and which fields of research could benefit from portal resources.

IV. Recommendations

Below are recommendations for the NAIRR portal team based on the findings presented in this report:

- **Increase awareness and promote AI resources to the research and education communities:** Most survey respondents indicated they are not currently using the NAIRR portal. Respondents noted in the open-ended responses that they either had limited knowledge of the NAIRR portal or were unsure how it could benefit their work. This knowledge gap limits the NAIRR portal's reach and potential impact, especially in the fast-evolving AI-related research and education fields. Many respondents expressed interests in tools, datasets, and collaborative opportunities that the NAIRR portal provides, but some were unsure how to locate and use them. To address this, it is recommended that the NAIRR portal team prioritize outreach to the broader research and education communities that use or could benefit from AI resources. Strategies could include hosting webinars, creating accessible guides or tutorials, collaborating with research institutions, and leveraging social media and academic networks. Additionally, the NAIRR portal team could consider establishing a presence by having its current users present NAIRR-portal facilitated work and cite NAIRR at conferences, in journals, and other widely accessed platforms. Furthermore, while most educators agreed that providing AI resources tailored for education and training on the NAIRR portal is *very* or *extremely* important, many expressed uncertainties about how to effectively integrate AI into their teaching. To address this, the NAIRR portal should establish a designated space for AI-related educational resources and best practices. These resources should focus on common needs among educators, such as data processing and analysis, as well as content generation for teaching, including course materials and code examples. Improving discoverability and communication will help researchers, educators, and practitioners understand how the NAIRR portal can support their work, ultimately increasing engagement and usage.
- **Simplify initial user experience while supporting advanced functionalities:** Given that most respondents have not used the NAIRR portal before, many expressed a need for an easy entry point to the portal. Lowering the barrier for first-time users—particularly for basic functions such as data sharing, requesting computing resource allocations, and accessing tools like Jupyter Notebooks—would greatly improve user adoption. Offering step-by-step tutorials for basic functions, for example, could ensure new users can quickly and intuitively perform fundamental tasks; and this can encourage engagement in the portal and exploration of other NAIRR portal resources. At the same time, some respondents indicated the need for more advanced features and complex toolsets to support their specialized research needs. Careful attention should be given to ensure that advanced features and complex toolsets do not overwhelm or complicate the experience for new users while still being readily accessible to those who require them.
- **Organize tools and resources for easy navigation and accessibility:** Respondents expressed interest in a wide variety of tools and resources being available on the NAIRR portal (e.g., data management and visualization, computing resource allocation, chat-based online support). While it is beneficial for the NAIRR portal to support these user needs, it is even more important to ensure that the platform's resources are organized in an intuitive and user-friendly manner. Users should be able to quickly locate what they need without feeling overwhelmed. To achieve this, the NAIRR portal team could consider grouping tools and resources based on their functionalities or primary focus areas, such as computing, data, or education. Implementing clear categories, filters, and search functions will further enhance discoverability. In addition to structural organization, attention should be given to the platform's visual design. Reducing large blocks of text, incorporating visual cues (e.g., icons or color-coded sections), and presenting information in a clean, uncluttered layout can help users navigate the platform more efficiently. By streamlining both the organization and presentation of resources, the NAIRR portal can better serve users with varying needs and levels of experience.

- **Offer user guides and training tailored to research needs:** Based on both closed-ended and open-ended survey responses, current and potential users of the NAIRR portal have varying research goals and levels of experience, with some coming from non-computing backgrounds and being new to AI and HPC tools. To support this wide range of user base, it is important to provide clear guidance that helps users identify resources that are most relevant to their research or educational objectives and use them effectively. Offering a variety of training options—such as tutorials, workshops tailored to specific projects or research goals, and tutoring—can help users start using the resources smoothly. Additionally, use cases and example workflows can serve as practical models for users to follow. By offering comprehensive and accessible training materials, the NAIRR portal can help users of all backgrounds leverage the NAIRR portal resources and the portal more effectively.
- **Keep gathering feedback from the community and monitor platform usage:** A recurring theme in the open-ended survey responses is the importance of continuously gathering feedback from users. Respondents emphasized that the NAIRR portal team should regularly interact with its user community to better understand whom it is serving and what users need. As the platform develops, new requests and challenges are likely to emerge. This is particularly important given the rapidly changing landscape of AI, where tools and trends can shift quickly. Ongoing communication with users will help the NAIRR portal team identify evolving needs and ensure that the resources it offers remain current and relevant. In addition to direct feedback from users, respondents recommended the team monitor usage data to gain insights into which resources are being utilized and where users encounter friction. By maintaining an active feedback loop and analyzing user engagement, the NAIRR portal team can keep making informed decisions to enhance its services and user experience.

Appendix B: Focus Group Topic Discussion Summaries

Topic 1: Envisioning features for the future NAIRR Portal

This focus group aimed to define the core functionalities and features that will best support the AI research community through the NAIRR (National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource) portal, including resource discovery, access management, collaboration tools, and user support services. Below are the summarized outcomes from the focus group discussion.

Understanding User Needs and Expectations

- Learning and Adoption Challenges
 - Environment setup difficulties: Participants consistently mentioned the challenge of configuring proper environments for AI work
 - Information overload: Difficulty navigating dispersed resources across different platforms and websites
 - Technical barriers: Varying levels of expertise create challenges in designing interfaces that serve both beginners and experts
 - Terminology confusion: Inconsistent AI terminology (e.g., deep learning vs. machine learning vs. generative AI) creates barriers
- Preferred Learning Methods
 - Structured learning environments: Conferences, meetups, and focused workshops were highlighted as effective
 - Hands-on practice: Short, task-specific tutorials with executable examples
 - Faded learning approach: Starting with considerable support that gradually decreases as expertise increases
 - Time-conscious resources: Clear time estimates for learning modules to manage expectations

Portal Features and Functionality

- Resource Organization and Discovery
 - One-stop shop for AI resources: Centralize access to models, datasets, test beds, and discussion forums
 - Domain-specific organization: Organize resources by research areas (materials science, social sciences, etc.)
 - Benchmarking tools: Include standard benchmarks and performance metrics for models
 - Example notebooks and code: Provide working, executable examples with clear documentation
- Computational Resources
 - Jupyter Notebooks integration: Widespread support for this familiar interface
 - Monitoring tools: Integrate capabilities similar to TensorBoard or Weights & Biases
 - Automatic checkpointing: Tools to help save model states and continue interrupted work
 - Energy consumption metrics: Tracking resources used for AI workloads
- Data Management
 - Centralized dataset repository: Eliminate need to manually download common datasets (MNIST, ImageNet, etc.)
 - Model versioning and provenance: Track model lineage, updates, and modifications

- AI alignment monitoring: Tools to detect model drift and determine when retraining is necessary
- FAIR principles integration: Support for findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability

User Support and Community Building

- Support Mechanisms
 - Differentiated office hours: Separate sessions for beginners vs. advanced users
 - One-on-one onboarding: Personalized guidance when starting new projects
 - AI-assisted help: AI support tools with human oversight
 - Comprehensive documentation: Clear explanations with realistic time estimates
- Educational Resources
 - Short-form video tutorials: Brief (1-3 minute) tutorials focused on specific tasks
 - Glossaries and definitions: Clear explanations of AI terminology and concepts
 - Domain-specific examples: Use cases and applications relevant to different fields
 - Skill building paths: Structured progression from beginner to advanced concepts

Additional Considerations

- Governance
 - AI alignment tools: Resources to monitor model drift and determine when retraining is needed
 - Log analysis capabilities: Tools to understand model behavior and detect potential harms
 - Cost transparency: Clear information about computational costs, especially for retraining
 - AI Bill of Rights integration: Guidelines for AI development and use
- Portal Organization
 - Categorized projects: Better organization of demonstration projects by type
 - User-friendly interfaces: Accessible design for users of all technical backgrounds
 - Integration with existing resources: Hugging Face, Kaggle, and other established platforms
 - Community discussion spaces: Forums for knowledge sharing and collaboration

Implementation Strategies

- Develop clearer categorization of existing pilot portal resources
- Explore providing centralized repositories for common datasets
- Implement model versioning and provenance tracking capabilities
- Design differentiated support systems for various user types
- Create domain-specific benchmarks and examples
- Establish standards for model documentation and updates

Topic 2: Workforce development and training in the classroom

This focus group aimed to define the core functionalities and features that will best support the AI research and education community through the NAIRR portal, including curriculum development, training resources, and workforce preparation. Below are the summarized outcomes from the focus group discussion.

Understanding AI Education Needs and Challenges

- Barriers to AI Integration in Education

- Negative perceptions of AI: Concerns about academic integrity and student reliance on generative AI
- Accessibility concerns: Many students and faculty lack coding skills necessary to engage with AI tools
- Resource limitations: Institutions without high-performance computing resources struggle to provide AI learning experiences
- Technical setup challenges: Setting up AI environments presents barriers even for technically skilled instructors
- Financial constraints: Some key tools (like ChatGPT 4.0) require credit cards or subscriptions, creating access barriers
- Rapidly evolving landscape: The field changes so quickly that staying current is challenging for educators
- Current Educational Approaches
 - Varied implementation methods: Faculty using AI for curriculum development, education, and project-based learning
 - Free resource utilization: Leveraging freely available resources like Intel modules and external training platforms
 - External certifications: Using platforms like Coursera, IBM, and Harvard's data science certification programs
 - Assignment integration: Faculty requiring students to use AI tools for specific tasks and projects
 - Interdisciplinary applications: Applying AI across different disciplines from accounting to emergency management

Portal Features and Functionality

- Desired Educational Resources
 - Certification pathways: Structured learning modules leading to recognized credentials
 - Progressive learning experiences: Leveled content (beginner to advanced) with clear advancement criteria
 - Short instructional videos: Brief, focused tutorials under 5 minutes on specific techniques or concepts
 - Low-code/no-code options: Tools accessible to users without extensive programming knowledge
 - Interactive simulations: Gamified learning experiences to engage students
 - Project-based templates: Ready-to-use class projects that incorporate AI tools
- Support Mechanisms
 - Campus ambassadors: Designated experts at institutions who can guide faculty in AI adoption
 - Success stories collection: Short videos of successful classroom implementations to inspire others
 - Peer-to-peer networking: Connecting educators implementing similar AI solutions across institutions
 - LMS integration: Tools that can easily integrate with existing learning management systems
 - Community forum: Space for educators to share experiences and troubleshoot challenges
 - Office hours: Virtual support sessions with subject matter experts

Curriculum and Program Development

- Evolving Curriculum Models
 - Distinguishing producers vs. consumers: Different tracks for those creating AI tools versus those using them
 - Certification programs: Micro-credentials and nano-learning opportunities as alternatives to traditional degrees
 - AI-specific tracks: New concentrations focusing on AI and robotics within existing degree programs
 - Preparatory sequences: Foundation courses that prepare students for more advanced AI applications
 - Interdisciplinary integration: Incorporating AI across disciplines rather than siloing in computer science
- Workforce Preparation
 - Job market alignment: Continuous monitoring of AI job postings to identify required skills
 - Upskilling opportunities: Short, focused learning experiences for professionals to adapt to changing needs
 - Considerations: Training on responsible AI use and potential biases
 - Transferable skills: Identifying core competencies that will remain valuable despite rapid technological change
 - Badge recognition: Portable credentials that can be verified and shared on professional platforms

Implementation Strategies

- Classroom Integration Approaches
 - Scaffolded assignments: Progressive introduction of AI tools through structured assignments
 - Virtual agents: Creating AI-powered simulations of company representatives for student interaction
 - Project-based learning: Having students create AI-augmented projects like illustrated children's books
 - Prompt engineering practice: Teaching students effective ways to communicate with AI systems
 - Badge systems: Recognizing student achievement through digital badges as they master various skills
- Assessment Considerations
 - Skills validation: Ensuring students can demonstrate mastery of specific AI competencies
 - Progress tracking: Methods to monitor advancement through learning modules
 - Integration with grading: Awarding course points for completion of certification modules
 - Performance metrics: Analyzing how AI tools impact student learning outcomes
 - Portfolio development: Helping students showcase their AI skills to potential employers

Topic 3: Resource providers' perspectives

This focus group aimed to define the core functionalities and features that will best support the AI research community through the NAIRR portal, with a specific focus on resource provider perspectives regarding resource discovery, access management, collaboration tools, and user support services. Below are the summarized outcomes from the focus group discussion.

Resource Provider Needs and Portal Integration

- Resource Classification and Discovery
 - Hardware vs. Capability-Based Description: Participants emphasized the need to shift from hardware-centric resource categorization to capability-focused descriptions aligned with AI/ML workflows
 - User-Oriented Classification: Recommendations for classifying resources by use case (e.g., training, inference, data preparation) rather than technical specifications
 - Workflow-Based Categorization: Organizing resources based on AI research workflows rather than hardware types would better serve researchers new to HPC environments
 - Resource Self-Management: Need for automated mechanisms allowing resource providers to update their own resource descriptions without manual intervention
- Technical Integration Challenges
 - Authentication Systems: Variability in authentication requirements across providers creates integration hurdles
 - Job Submission Mechanisms: Differences between traditional HPC batch systems and cloud environments like Kubernetes require flexible approaches
 - Security Standards: Different institutional security policies create barriers to implementing centralized functionality
 - Manual Processes: Too many processes currently requiring manual intervention, creating workload issues for staff

User Support and Onboarding

- User Experience Improvements
 - Streamlined Allocation Process: Recent changes allowing PIs to attest for entire teams will simplify onboarding
 - Interactive Access: Need for simplified access mechanisms like Jupyter notebooks for users unfamiliar with HPC environments
 - Data Transfer Support: Users frequently struggle with moving large datasets to compute resources
 - Researcher Expertise Levels: Portal should accommodate different user levels from novice to expert with appropriate interfaces
- Support Challenges
 - Staffing Limitations: Resource providers received hardware supplements but inadequate support for additional staff
 - User Needs: AI researchers come from varied backgrounds with different levels of HPC knowledge
 - Training Requirements: Need for interactive training sessions beyond documentation and videos
 - Technical Knowledge Gap: Significant disparity between traditional HPC users and AI researchers in terms of technical background

Data Management and Access

- Data-Centric Considerations
 - Data Commons Capabilities: Need for shared repositories of common datasets to avoid redundant transfers
 - Sensitive Data Handling: Requirements for handling protected data (e.g., HIPAA) differ between providers

- Multi-Modal Data: Need to support various data types, particularly for healthcare and other specialized research
- Model Integration: Challenges with importing models from different sources, especially regarding export control restrictions
- Resource Optimization
 - Right-Sizing Workloads: Users frequently request high-end GPUs without understanding alternatives
 - Resource Usage Monitoring: Researchers need better visibility into their resource consumption
 - Framework Compatibility: Ensuring software frameworks are compatible with specific hardware resources
 - Compute-Data Proximity: Challenges with data locality and storage relative to compute resources

Collaboration Opportunities

- Community Building
 - Cross-Resource Collaboration: Enabling researchers to find complementary resources for their projects
 - Expert Connections: Linking researchers with subject matter experts (e.g., SKYPE teams) relevant to their projects
 - Educational Opportunities: Supporting in-person and online training to build community knowledge
 - Researcher Matchmaking: Helping researchers find collaborators with complementary expertise
- Integration with Other Initiatives
 - NAIRR Secure Integration: Unclear relationship between secure resources and main NAIRR platform
 - Better Coordination: Need for improved coordination between NAIRR and other NSF programs like ACCESS
 - Standardized APIs: Developing consistent interfaces for resource providers to integrate with the portal
 - Multi-Agency Integration: Supporting researchers with grants from multiple agencies (e.g., NIH and NSF)

Implementation Strategies

- Login Button: Create a direct connection through the NAIRR portal homepage for users to access allocations
- Resource Categorization: Implement more user-friendly resource categories based on capabilities and workflows
- User Documentation: Develop consistent, clear documentation for resources with particular attention to AI-specific needs
- Feedback Mechanisms: Create streamlined methods for users to provide feedback about resources
- Automation Development: Build automated systems for resource allocation and management to reduce manual processes
- Data Framework: Develop a comprehensive framework for making data more accessible across resources
- Staff Support: Ensure adequate funding for support staff as NAIRR grows beyond the pilot phase

- Expanded Community Engagement: Broaden stakeholder involvement to include more research communities

Topic 4: Conducting research via NAIRR Portal

This focus group aimed to define the core functionalities and features that will best support the AI research community through the NAIRR portal, focusing on resource discovery, access management, collaboration tools, and user support services. Below are the summarized outcomes from the focus group discussion.

Information Discovery and Learning Resources

- Approaches to Learning New Concepts
 - Community-Based Learning: Participation in interest groups, workshops, and professional networks for keeping up with rapidly evolving AI developments
 - Curated Resources: Need for opinionated guides that filter the overwhelming volume of AI information and provide reliable direction
 - Domain-Specific Expert Networks: Leveraging communities like Slack channels where practitioners can validate information and provide context
 - Applied Learning: Following funding opportunities and building expertise through practical application rather than abstract exploration
- Challenges in Staying Current
 - Overwhelming Pace: The rapid evolution of AI technologies makes it difficult to stay current with developments like DeepSeek
 - Scattered Resources: Information is distributed across many platforms without a central repository
 - Quality Variability: Difficulty distinguishing authoritative resources from less reliable ones
 - Lack of Domain Translation: Resources often don't adequately translate AI concepts for specific domain applications

Portal Design and Functionality

- Resource Organization and Discovery
 - Capability-Based Classification: Participants emphasized the need to organize resources by capabilities rather than hardware specifications
 - Blueprint Architectures: Creating reference examples showing end-to-end pipelines for specific research scenarios
 - Scalable Solutions: Providing pathways that work on local resources but can scale to larger infrastructure when needed
 - Data Commons Approach: Centralizing access to commonly used datasets rather than requiring individual connections
- Collaboration Features
 - Interdisciplinary Data Sharing: Tools for different disciplines to share, comment on, and collaborate with data
 - Version Control: Maintaining a record of analysis evolution with proper documentation of changes
 - Integrated Discussion: Capabilities beyond Google Docs for collaborating on documents and data analysis

- Visualization Tools: Support for complex visualizations that integrate technical and organizational systems
- AI Integration into the Portal
 - Virtual AI Assistants: Using AI within the portal itself to guide users to appropriate resources
 - Structured Output Tools: Libraries that structure AI outputs for easier integration into research workflows
 - RAG Capabilities: Supporting retrieval-augmented generation with user-provided documents and publications
 - Model Comparison Features: Tools to benchmark multiple AI models with standardized evaluation metrics

Resource Access and Utilization

- Technical Infrastructure
 - HPC Access: Many participants rely on a combination of local computing and high-performance computing resources
 - Resource Discovery: Need for clearer information about what resources are available and how to use them
 - Allocation Process: Improved guidance about the steps from getting an allocation to actually accessing resources
 - Streamlined Onboarding: Clearer pathways for new users to get started with different types of resources
- Data Management and Integration
 - Cross-Repository Access: Connecting to various data repositories including NIH datasets
 - NIH Security Requirements: Consideration of the NIST 800-171 compliance needs for controlled access data
 - Interdisciplinary Data Needs: Support for working with data across different domains and formats
 - Data Preparation Guidance: Resources to help researchers prepare and clean their data for AI applications

User Support and Community Building

- Educational Resources
 - Skill Transfer Support: Tutorials and guidance for transitioning between programming languages and frameworks
 - In-Person Workshops: Hands-on sessions at conferences to build community and lower barriers to entry
 - Progressive Learning Paths: Structured learning resources for different expertise levels
 - Applied Examples: Real-world examples demonstrating AI applications in various domains
- Community Engagement
 - Slack Channel: Creating a dedicated Slack channel for NAIRR users to communicate and share information
 - Portal Ambassadors: Designated experts who can guide faculty and researchers in using the portal effectively
 - Regular Communication: Newsletter and updates to keep the community informed about new resources and capabilities

- Feedback Mechanisms: User-friendly ways to provide feedback beyond technical support tickets

Implementation Strategies

- Resource Organization: Restructure the portal to make resource information more prominent and discoverable
- Clear Documentation: Provide step-by-step guidance for allocation processes and resource access
- Community Building: Establish communication channels like Slack for user interaction
- Feedback System: Create intuitive mechanisms for users to provide input beyond technical support
- Interdisciplinary Coordination: Develop frameworks for connecting resources across different domains and agencies
- Blueprint Libraries: Create template workflows for common AI research scenarios that can be easily adapted
- Outreach to Underserved Institutions: Proactively engage with primarily undergraduate institutions and researchers with limited resources
- Integration with Existing Platforms: Develop APIs and standards for connecting with domain-specific platforms like KBase

Topic 5: Training and learning modalities

This focus group aims to define the core functionalities and features that will best support the AI research community through the NAIRR portal, including resource discovery, access management, collaboration tools, and user support services. Below are the summarized outcomes from the focus group discussion.

Understanding User Needs and Expectations

- Challenges in Accessing AI Training
 - Information overload: Participants noted the difficulty of navigating the "fire hose" of information with no official, comprehensive resource.
 - Rapid technological change: Difficulty keeping up with evolving tools and frameworks was highlighted as a major challenge.
 - Terminology confusion: The complex and inconsistent terminology in AI (foundation models vs. LLMs vs. deep learning) creates barriers to entry.
 - Lack of guidance: Limited access to mentors and structured learning paths.
 - Cost barriers: Access to necessary platforms and tools often requires financial investment.
 - Resource limitations: Limited access to GPUs, databases, and proprietary tools.
 - Time constraints: Learning AI is often not part of regular job responsibilities.
- Desired Skills and Knowledge
 - Model interpretation techniques: Understanding black box AI models through techniques like SHAP, LIME, and counterfactual analysis.
 - AI auditing skills: Ability to quantify biases in datasets and analyze validity of outputs without requiring deep data science expertise.
 - Explainable AI: Tools to understand why and how models are making specific decisions.
 - Resource efficiency: Monitoring GPU usage, training curves, and optimizing computational resources.

- Quantum computing applications: Understanding how quantum algorithms are shaping AI.
- Portal Support Goals
 - Comprehensive glossary: Clear explanations of AI terminology and concepts.
 - Efficient onboarding: Resources to help researchers quickly adapt to different infrastructures.
 - Monitoring tools: Resources for checking GPU usage and training progress.

Preferred Training Modalities

- Preferred Learning Formats
 - Mixed approach: Participants described starting with structured online courses (Coursera, edX, Udemy) for basics, then progressing to research papers for depth, and finally implementing small projects.
 - Video tutorials: YouTube was mentioned as a powerful resource for learning.
 - Workshops and webinars: Both academic and industry-led sessions.
 - Tool-specific documentation: Resources from organizations like the European Center for weather prediction.
- Importance of Computational Resources
 - Critical for complex work: Hands-on access to GPUs described as essential for meaningful learning.
 - Scale challenges: Some institutions lack adequate computational resources for training, limiting what students can learn.
 - Regional disparities: Some regions have very limited GPU resources (one participant mentioned their region had no more than six GPUs before recent efforts).

Content and Curriculum Design

- Foundational Topics to Include
 - Responsible AI: How to safely use data and avoid potential societal harm.
 - AI literacy: Understanding capabilities and limitations of AI tools.
 - Human-centered design: Creating AI systems that address real-world problems.
 - Monitoring and evaluating models: Understanding training behavior and interpreting results.
- Value of Tailored Courses
 - Strong support for different levels: Recognition that different users (from beginners to experts) need different resources.
 - Domain-specific applications: Weather prediction was mentioned as an example where specialized AI knowledge is valuable.
 - Interdisciplinary approach: Courses that connect AI to healthcare, geography, linguistics, and other fields.

Integration with Workforce Development

- Supporting Career Advancement
 - Mentorship programs: Connect students with mentors and career coaches for one-on-one learning.
 - Project examples: Share successful NAIRR projects as case studies.
 - Internships and fellowships: Create opportunities for practical experience.
 - Standards integration: Incorporate open science standards and FAIR data practices.
- Value of Certifications

- Conditional support: Valuable if employers recognize and value them.
- Specialized certifications: Particularly useful for areas like accountability.
- Research-specific badges: Distinguish research-focused skills from industrial applications.
- Fellowship requirements: Specify which badges would make someone eligible for specific fellowships or internships.

Future Needs and Open Feedback

- AI for all: Tools that support assistive technologies.
 - Governance: Frameworks for responsible AI and human oversight.
 - Reproducibility: Containerization (singularity containers) and modernization tools.
 - Explainable AI and uncertainty quantification: Building trust through model transparency.
 - Multilingual support: Making AI tools accessible across language barriers.
 - Accessibility features: Supporting users with all abilities
- Making NAIRR Portal the Preferred Platform
 - Human element: Access to experts behind the portal for consultation.
 - Interactive tutorials: Game-like tutorials that show users what they're about to do in 30 seconds or less.
 - Community building: Creating connections between researchers and educators.
 - Strong foundation: Emphasizing responsible use and human oversight.
- Additional Insights
 - Some participants noted that AI users don't necessarily need deep technical knowledge about the models, but need to understand their limitations.
 - Participants observed a shift away from HPC training toward prompt engineering in many educational contexts.
 - The group emphasized the need for democratizing AI tools through open-source frameworks and accessible platforms.
 - Several participants highlighted the importance of recognizing regional differences in resource availability when designing training programs.

Topic 6: Portal design and support

This focus group aims to define the core functionalities and features that will best support the AI research community through the NAIRR portal, including user navigation, communication tools, and support considerations. Below are the summarized outcomes from the focus group discussion.

Portal Design Elements

- Positive Elements to Include
 - Clear Navigation Structure: Organized resources into intuitive categories with clear section labels
 - Customizable Dashboard: Allow users to personalize their experience with bookmarks and frequently accessed resources
 - Accessibility Features: Colorblind-friendly design with good contrast ratios
 - Text with Icons: Include descriptive text alongside all icons for clarity
 - Account Management: Integration with institutional logins rather than creating new accounts
 - Mobile Responsiveness: Clear communication about what functions work on different devices

- Elements to Avoid
 - Dense Information: Too much information density makes content difficult to process
 - Hover Navigation: Disruptive hover menus that interfere with browsing
 - Formal/Technical Language: Overly complex terminology creates barriers for new users
 - Excessive Notifications: Over-notification leads users to ignore all alerts

Communication & Collaboration Features

- Support Mechanisms
 - Ticketing System: For complex issues requiring investigation
 - Office Hours: Regular, scheduled times for one-on-one support with subject matter experts
 - Community Channels: Integration with Slack/Discord for user communication
 - Short Tutorial Videos: Brief (1-3 minute) instructional videos for specific tasks
 - Documentation: Comprehensive, well-maintained documentation with examples and executable code
- Collaborative Tools
 - Shared Resources: Ability to share notebooks, data, and code
 - Resource Status: Clear communication about system outages and maintenance
 - Metadata Sharing: Tools to document the connections between datasets, algorithms, and environments
 - DOI Support: Automated DOI generation for published research is highly valued

Community Considerations

- Supporting All Users
 - Written Language: Use 8th-grade level language and avoid jargon where possible
 - Domain-Specific Organization: Organize resources by research areas and disciplines
 - Multiple Learning Paths: Different entry points for various skill levels
 - Multiple Languages: Support for content in various languages
 - Faculty Development: Support for educators who need to teach AI concepts
 - Visual Elements: Use infographics and visual aids to improve comprehension
- Educational Resources
 - Short Format Videos: Brief tutorials focused on single tasks or concepts
 - Interactive Examples: Executable code examples alongside explanations
 - Community-Driven Content: Resources developed based on community feedback
 - Glossaries: Clear explanation of terminology and concepts
 - Mentorship Programs: Connect researchers with subject matter experts

Implementation Strategies

- Design for Multiple User Types: Create different entry paths for beginners, educators, and advanced researchers
- Prioritize Documentation: Dedicate resources to creating and maintaining comprehensive documentation
- Implement FAIR Principles: Support for persistent identifiers and rich metadata to enhance reproducibility
- Create Community Spaces: Facilitate communication between users through integrated channels
- Develop Short-Form Content: Focus on brief, task-specific tutorials rather than lengthy guides
- Use Community Supportive Language: Avoid technical jargon and use plain language where possible

- Support Customization: Allow users to personalize their experience based on their needs and preferences
- Incorporate Human Support: Complement technical resources with office hours and expert assistance

Appendix C: Workshop Organizers and Schedule

Organizing Committee:

- Sandra Gesing, University of California San Diego
- Maytal Dahan, University of Texas Austin
- Claire Stirm, University of California San Diego
- Linda Hayden, Elizabeth City State University
- Janae Baker, University of California San Diego
- Juliana Casavan, Casavan Consulting
- Stephanie Baker, University of Texas Austin
- Yiwen Yang, University of Texas Austin
- Lisa Garbrecht, University of Texas Austin
- Chante Powell, University of California San Diego
- Cindy Wong, University of California San Diego

Schedule:

Tuesday, February 4, 8:00AM – 5:00PM: NAIRR Portal Workshop Meeting Day 1

- 8:00 am - Breakfast/Registration
- 9:00 am - Intro to NAIRR program and workshop logistics
- 9:15 am - Workshop Welcome Keynote
- 9:30 am - NAIRR Pilot Portal Update and Outcome of SGX3 NAIRR survey and focus groups
- 10:00 am - Break
- 10:30 am - Breakout sessions
- 12:30 pm - Lunch
- 1:30 pm - Design Thinking/Braintrust
- 3:00 pm - Break
- 3:30 pm - Group Presentations
- 4:30 pm - Group Discussions and wrap up day one
- 5:00 pm - Conclude
- 6:00 pm - Social dinner/Reception at Ridgewalk Social (3-5 min walk from SDSC)

Wednesday, February 5, 8:00AM – 3:00PM: NAIRR Portal Workshop Meeting Day 2

- 8:00 am - Breakfast
- 9:00 am - Day 1 Recap and Day 2 workshop logistics
- 9:15 am - Breakout sessions
- 10:15 am - Break
- 10:45 am - Group Presentations
- 11:15 am - Group Session
- 12:00 pm - Invited Faculty Keynote by Julian McAuley
- 12:30 pm - Lunch
- 1:30 pm - Group Presentations
- 2:45 pm - Closing remarks from SGX3
- 3:00 pm - Adjourn
- 3:00 pm: Voluntary: Tour and History of SDSC and Data Center

Appendix D: Workshop Attendees

Name	Institution	Role
Alejandro Strachan	Purdue University	Faculty
Amal Perera	University of Connecticut	Researcher
Amit Chourasia	University of California, Los Angeles	Staff
Amit Majumdar	University of California, San Diego	Researcher
Amy Sitapati	University of California, San Diego	Faculty
Andrea Zonca	University of California San Diego	Staff
Andrew Pasquale	MGHPCC	Staff
Ashley Atkins	University of California San Diego	Staff
Bakhyt Alipova	University of Kentucky	Researcher
Beulah Karrolla	Texas Advanced Computing Center	Researcher
Caleb Reinking	University of Notre Dame	Staff
Charlie Dey	The University of Texas at Austin	Staff
Christian Garcia	The University of Texas at Austin	Staff
Claire Stirm	University of California San Diego	Staff
Colleen Megowan-Romanowicz	American Modeling Teachers Association	Researcher
Dan Stanzione	The University of Texas at Austin	Staff
David Danks	University of California San Diego	Faculty
David Hancock	Indiana University	Staff
David Hart	NSF NCAR	Staff
Dhableswar K (DK) Panda	The Ohio State University	Faculty
Ellie Alhajjar	RAND	Researcher
Ernest Holmes	Google / CodeHouse	Staff

Eroma Abeysinghe	Georgia Institute of Technology	Faculty
Henry Li	San Diego State University	Staff
Ho-Joon Lee	Yale University	Faculty
Hovakim Grabski	University of California San Diego	Researcher
Ilkay De Callafon	University of California San Diego	Faculty
Ilya Shunko	University of California San Diego	Staff
Inna Kouper	Indiana University	Faculty
Jack Fenwick	Amazon Web Services	Staff
Jack Smith	Marshall University	Staff
Janae Baker	University of California San Diego	Staff
Javier Hernandez-Nicolau	University of California San Diego	Staff
Jeanette Sperhac	University of California San Diego	Staff
Jessica Hill	Google	Staff
Jiyin Zhang	University of Idaho	Researcher
Joel Bretheim	Princeton University	Staff
John Towns	NCSA/University of Illinois	Staff
Joseph Aneke	Hampton University	Faculty
Julian McAuley	University of California San Diego	Faculty
Karan Vahi	USC/ISI CiCompass, NAIRR Pilot, Pegasus	Staff
Katherine Riley	Argonne National Laboratory	Staff
Kenton McHenry	University of Illinois	Researcher
Kyle Chard	University of Chicago	Researcher
La Tasha Roberts	Austin Community College	Staff
Layla Freeborn	University of Colorado Boulder	Staff
Linda Hayden	Elizabeth City State University	Faculty

Lisa Perez	Texas A&M University	Staff
Lissie Fein	MGHPCC	Other
Lloyd Mitchell	Elizabeth City State University	Faculty
Manikya Swathi Vallabhajosyula	The Ohio State University	Student
Maria Jaromin	University of Illinois Urbana Champaign	Staff
Marinus Pennings	Texas A&M University	Staff
Marisa Brazil	Arizona State University	Staff
Martine De Cock	University of Washington Tacoma	Faculty
Mary Thomas	University of California at San Diego	Staff
Maytal Dahan	The University of Texas at Austin	Staff
Melissa Harden	Center for Research Computing, University of Notre Dame	Staff
Michael Kio	University of Maryland	Faculty
Michael Norman	University of California San Diego	Faculty
Munene Kanampiu	Winston-Salem State University	Faculty
Nelofar Qulizada	University of Arkansas	Student
Niall Gaffney	Texas Advanced Computing Center	Staff
Nizar Alsharari	Jackson State University	Faculty
Paola Buitrago	Carnegie Mellon University	Researcher
Rahil Ashtari Mahini	Texas Advanced Computing Center	Student
Rajesh Kalyanam	Purdue University	Researcher
Richard Gerber	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	Staff
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Appendix E: NAIRR Portal Workshop Problem Statements

1. How might the portal keep users engaged in the AI-research community?

During the workshop, the attendees focused on how a graduate-student researcher would discover and use the NAIRR Portal to learn about AI and available resources during the workshop. When thinking through how the graduate student would discover the portal, they ideated around marketing materials, social media, PI recommendations, school recommendations, community, and internet search. The end goal would point the student to the training section of the portal. This training area would offer keywords and prompts with lists and a faceted navigation and full descriptions of training to learn about the NAIRR AI resources available to the student to learn. The student would have access to metadata on how much time it takes to complete the training, format of training (live, Zoom, documentation, interactive notebook, etc.), topics covered, learning outcomes, software, requirements, objectives of the training, ratings, reviews, last verified, and recently viewed materials. Through this training area of the portal, students and other audiences would have smoother experiences onboarding to community resources and approaching AI learning.

2. How might the portal facilitate collaboration on AI-related research on institutions and disciplines?

During the workshop, with this problem statement, the attendees focused on inexperienced PIs within the community that are working with educational or research tools. The focus of the design thinking was a simplified user interface for onboarding researchers to launch right into the NAIRR Portal and their work. For example, after completing a login, the researcher would see a dashboard that has suggestions for steps they can complete that day from recently completed tasks or tasks that they might complete next from the allocation needs, a module that shows their collaborators, a module that shows their sandbox, a module for their tools/workflows that are active, and a module for open resource selection. From the resource selection, as an example, they could launch a Jupyter Notebook. Then provide feedback and suggestions for other users - such as their collaborators - on what they learned when running their model. The concept of having collaborators right in the NAIRR Portal with the PI allows them to create a project space for themselves to work within, select a team of their collaborators by project, and associate the appropriate tools/modules for their team during important phases of work.

3. How might the portal improve and streamline a user's current processes within the NAIRR ecosystem?

During the workshop, participants focused on the needs of post-docs, particularly around automating manual data processing tasks. They explored how post-docs typically follow a process of searching, comparing, defining, evaluating, planning, and ultimately requesting the data needed for their research. The group developed parameters to help map data requirements to post-doc needs through intuitive interfaces, incorporating elements such as data size, model type, memory requirements, number of iterations, file formats, software licenses, and compute scale. Their proposed design concept was a job builder that uses these parameters to generate summaries, helping post-docs select the most suitable solution for their research.

4. How might the portal tailor support to a wide-range of user's needs at varying levels of engagement?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on Ph.D students that are in disciplines that typically underutilize HPC resources but are located in fields with higher

quantities of data (for example, linguistics). Their motivations as students are to publish, apply new tech to their discipline, and become competitive and employable. Thus, the team proposed a design of an interface that starts with first posing the problem that the student would like to work on which prompts curation of solutions. The student has the ability to add to their workflow a sandbox with data and then execute results, all while seeing prompts along the way to guide them.

5. How might the portal provide guidance to effectively use NAIRR resources?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on PIs with an idea of what research or project they are focusing on but a need to select the resource for the project. The team of attendees ideated on a resource-discovery system that had the researcher identify through their project use-case or abstract the criteria of the project and then would present a recommender system for resources they can select for their allocation. The recommender system would also have an AI-chat service.

6. How might a portal feature help researchers learn to use new tools and methodologies to apply to their research?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on PIs/researchers learning to use AI tools and methods to apply to their work. The attendees in this group proposed an AI-powered recommender to identify new tools and methodologies. The steps involved in the experience would enable training through tutorials, share case studies to apply further adoptive learning about the tools and methodologies, and share a getting started (1st win) with best practice examples from the community and matchmaking expertise. The AI recommender would have an experience of sharing what AI tool or method you are interested in, share where you would like to run the tool, and then the recommender would provide the described supportive learning materials to get started. The goal of the recommender would also be competency of the environment of the NAIRR ecosystem and the steps to get a supplement/access resources, run tutorials, get data, and train/test models.

7. How might the portal enable educators to teach AI to their students?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on post-secondary faculty with beginner-mid familiarity with AI tools. They also thought of this audience as being multi-disciplinary and early stage careers with values in knowledge sharing, seeking tenure, academic integrity, publications, inspiring others, and continuous learning. The challenges shared around this group of audience is that they have a hard time finding a good/validated curriculum, department is resistant to change, lack of money/time to keep up with industry changes, and lack support from their institution to adopt all the solutions available so needed focused solutions that are easily adoptable. The design idea was to present a user friendly curriculum, training, and tools space that is AI aligned. The design of the interface would need search filtration for metadata of the curriculum, a chatbot to enable smooth english language prompts towards discovery and recommendations, and the ability to select pre-built curriculum packages (courses) that educators could apply. Some of the metadata that was explored in this design was types of implementation of the curriculum (training, course, tool, etc.), topic areas, computational languages taught, and other descriptors to summarize the contents of the curriculum.

8. How might the portal facilitate collaboration on AI-related research for educators across institutions and disciplines?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on educators tasked with implementing AI in their courses at their institution. The challenges this team described for this audience were similar to problem statement 7 (see above) but also focused on trust of resources and inconsistency across available curriculum solutions today. The design focused on connecting them through communities of practice and support. The team brainstormed an input portal interface that profiles researchers and educators by connecting to services like ResearchGate and Google Scholar, then generates personalized recommendations for content and learning materials aligned with their interests and curriculum goals.

9. How might the portal facilitate the sharing of research tools and products (models, data, etc.) developed to assist in research and education?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group, focused on a graduate-student audience segment with a domain-science background—not in computer science. The motivation for the graduate student was to use new insight that leads to publication for their research work. With the student's proximity to their peers, they would use the resources familiar to their professors and mentors or use cost-driven solutions with work mostly done in a shortened time frame. The values this audience segment cares about is being community-aligned with academic integrity, creativity, and impact. The design recommendation was a natural-language interface that would allow graduate students to ask for data, models, or methods related to a specific research challenge they were working on, and the LLM would provide an output of that request from the NAIRR resources available to that student's allocations. For example, the student could ask for data and receive outputs linked to where they could collect the data they are seeking. By enabling a chat service for discovery, the students can perform a simpler and more timely initial review enabling trust, usability, and relevance. The student then could share the outputs with their advisor for review and enable the chat window to remain open for further chatting once they have feedback from their advisor. Additionally, they can use the selection as a point of reference for their work.

10. How might the portal integrate FAIR standards?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on a graduate-student audience segment with a domain-science background—not in computer science. The motivation was to enable recognition for work and expertise. The values and challenges were very similar to the prior mapped audience segment shared in problem statement 9 (see above) but also focused on challenges accessing private data or creating data due to lack of experience and that the data is not self-describing or can lack acknowledgement. The design recommended by the attendees in this group focused on a dashboard for the data used by the graduate student to illustrate FAIR principles and identify the principles that the student is following. The dashboard could highlight the datasets of the student, the project they are on, and the public datasets with FAIR badges and ratings. Additionally, it could include alerts or flags of where there is missing information (e.g., missing descriptors, missing DOIs, etc.). The ability to submit metadata of existing datasets was also proposed and would enable the community to see where there were opportunities to contribute.

11. How might the portal support the development of new services and tools for AI-related research?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on a mid-to-advanced-level computer science researcher early in their career. Motivations included the ability to work in isolation and to tune existing practices instead of training. Their values focused on good papers, recognition,

staying ahead, funding, and finding talent. The design this team of attendees proposed was a similar AI-chat service to 'what, where, and how,' enabling the researcher to provide the area of research, goal of work, annotated resources needed, benchmarks, data needed, and timeframe. The chat service would then select the NAIRR resources, draft the proposal for the workflow, and select alternative resources to propose back to the researcher. Additionally the service would generate scripts if the solutions met the researchers standards. The goals of this service would elevate the landscape around AI-research gathering and planning. Enabling the service to learn from available resources (e.g., readthedocs, experimental runs, training, prepared data), and in turn supporting the researcher by generating semi-complete-to-complete solutions to steps in the process of building a proposal or building a model that targets the researcher's goal would support efficient research.

12. How can the portal promote AI practices?

During the workshop, the attendees of this group focused on instructors who need AI resources for a classroom setting. The challenges in this area focused on terminology to associate with datasets, models, and methods that would inform the educator and also researchers on trustworthy resources as they search. The described design proposed tips and hints to be available in the user interface in order to explain to users how the data or model was established. The values identified for this audience segment were focused on publication, intellectual-property protection, and societal benefit at no harm. The motivations were to drive the need of resources to address their AI problem, improve the speed to solution, improve impact, collaboration, and exposure. Challenges expressed were defined as what actions to take to ensure that the AI work is meeting community standards and compliance (e.g., legal, institutional, funding, etc.). Additionally, the group raised questions: Will data gathering/sharing ensure credibility, will discovering resources have implications, and will they be able to use the portal with clear verification and instructions?